

Centre[4] Art and Research Services: Artists with an Interest in Research

centre[4]
art + research

Abstract

This table is intended for those who identify somewhere within the following:

- Artists who want to lead a research project within their art practice,
- Artists who have an interest in telling the story of/reflecting on what happened within an art project or practice, and/or
- Artists who articulate their art practice as research in some capacity, such as a way of exploring, form of inquiry, or way of creating knowledge.

If you are considering working with Centre[4] Art and Research (C[4]), we can set up a meeting to hear a bit about your project or practice and to talk about the services that C[4] can provide. C[4] offers different levels of support/facilitation and an accompanying fee structure.

Administrative Details

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Published: January 2024

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DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10592833>

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Service	Description	Fee
<p>Consultation A: Exploring and Clarifying the project</p>	<p>Consultation: C[4] will meet with you to think through and/or hear about the role research plays in the project or practice. Here are some examples of questions we might ask:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What does research mean in the context of your project? • What does engagement with research do for your project or practice or for you as an artist? 	<p>Consultation A is a free service. Along with the consultation, it also includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direction to C[4] tools and resources, • Relevant project examples, • Referrals to funding sources, and • Preliminary discussion of potential roles for C[4] in your project.
<p>After Consultation A, you may decide one of many paths to move forward. This could include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) not continuing with the project; b) continuing the project without support of C[4]; c) continuing the project with the initial support of C[4], such as that offered in Consultation B. 		
<p>Consultation B: What would be supportive to this project or practice?</p>	<p>Consultation: After our initial meeting, we will work with you to identify or clarify your needs for this project or practice and to clarify the role C[4] will play in providing support.</p> <p>As artist's research is understood and taken up in many different ways, it will be important to clarify how you understand the role of research in relation to what kinds of support you are looking for.</p> <p>The following are some examples of frameworks for understanding support:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Looking for ways to explore, document, and understand what my art practice <i>is doing</i> in the world/in my community... 	<p>Consultation B is a free service.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Looking for ways to share, tell or reflect upon what is meaningful about an art project, • Exploring what it is that made this art practice or project impactful or generative, • Wanting to create an artist statement that outlines my process of research/ inquiry, and • Looking for ways to assess or evaluate the effects of my art or art practice (for myself, or for a community partner or funder). 	
	<p>Examples: Providing relevant examples.</p> <p>Once we have clarified where research fits within your project, C[4] will provide some examples of art projects or artistic practices that take up research in different ways.</p> <p>C[4] will also provide access to publicly available research reports, websites, and more, as relevant.</p>	
	<p>Connection: Connecting to McMaster researcher(s) who is/are working in the Artist's field of interest.</p> <p>C[4] will explain the hoped-for project and collaboration to a few artists who might be a good fit and where there seems promise on both sides. We will facilitate a meeting to talk through the potential collaboration.</p> <p>Connection might also include outreach via C[4], Centre[3] for Artistic + Social Practice, and McMaster University Community Research Platform (CRP) websites. C[4] and CRP staff may also provide connections via personal knowledge.</p>	

	<p>Resources: Providing resources to support equitable partnerships (resources are free and available on the C[4] website).</p> <p>Here is a list of the written resources C[4] provides:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Examples of services in action ● Partnership agreement guidelines ● Arts output, process, and data sharing agreement ● Fee structure guideline ● Ethical considerations when engaging with the arts guideline ● Collaborative partnership checklist ● Sample workshop templates for arts involved research practices 	
<p>After Consultation B, you may decide to move forward with or without the support of C[4]. Your project might involve:</p> <p>a) continuing the project without support of C[4];</p> <p>b) continuing the project with C[4] continued facilitation as in Consultation C.</p>		
<p>Consultation C: Ongoing Consultation, Reflection, and Documentation process</p>	<p>Consultation: As the project shifts and grows, C[4] will potentially (depending on the level of C[4] support you've decided to use) provide ongoing consultation and reflection as a way of providing support. This includes addressing needs/concerns that arise within a project.</p> <p>Ongoing consultation also involves working with you to develop a plan for ongoing documentation of your project or practice.</p> <p>*see note regarding documentation process</p> <p>Follow-Up: Reflecting on the process.</p> <p>Once your project is finished, C[4] will provide follow up/offer reflection on how the project went. Some questions we might ask are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How did this project go? ● What's next? ● What kind of support could you use more or less of? 	<p>Consultation C will have a fee attached.</p> <p>The fee for services will be determined on a case-by-case basis.</p>

*Something we've noticed in developing this work is that if documentation of a project is left until the end, it tends to land in the academic and/or less artistic realm. For example, academic articles and reports often provide much of the public facing information about a project. We want to encourage and support creative, ongoing processes of documentation, so that the *process* of the project can also be made visible and potentially celebrated!